

MASTER 1st Open Call: Successful Completion of the Execution Phase

The MASTER project announces the completion of the execution phase of its 1st Open Call, which ran from November 2024 until October 2025. The call supported the development and validation of Extended Reality (XR) technologies aimed at improving industrial and educational training.

Through this initiative, 17 projects from across Europe were selected to contribute new XR functionalities and training solutions to the MASTER platform. Each project has been tested and validated by students, which represented both industrial and academic stakeholders, from various industrial sectors..

Advancing XR Applications for Training and Safety

During the execution phase, the selected projects developed XR-based applications focused on safety, human-robot interaction, and efficient robot programming. Their results demonstrate practical ways to apply XR technology in real industrial environments.

Key developments include:

- eXRercise: Provided realistic VR training for robot operators, preparing them for hazards such as fires and malfunctions. AI and machine learning assess performance and stress in real time.
- EMPOWER: Improved workplace safety with modular XR tools for real-time visualisation, assistance, and safety assessment.
- VTBM Station: Used hybrid XR environments and motion tracking to improve ergonomics and reduce injury risks in tyre manufacturing.
- i-MAR-XR: Developed maritime safety training through digital twins of cargo ships and interactive XR experiences.
- MRP: Enabled precise robot control through haptic gloves, supporting intuitive programming and improved adaptability.
- MANIPULAY XR: Offered a VR learning environment for configuring and programming robotic manipulators.
- WAVE: Supported natural human-robot interaction using IMU-based devices and haptic gloves.
- XR4Human-SERVE 5.0: Created an XR-based assembly workstation that enhances productivity and worker comfort.
- DREAMER: Added a tool for 3D content creation and virtual training scenarios to the MASTER platform.
- Ergon-XR: Focused on ergonomic XR training to reduce risks and improve efficiency in automated manufacturing.
- XR4MCR: Provided a multi-user XR training platform for robot maintenance and skill development.
- REACH: Improved collaboration between real and virtual robots through multi-user VR/MR applications.

- V-PAINT: Introduced Mixed Reality tools for faster and more intuitive robotic programming.
- AAXLP: Connected AI voice interfaces with XR tools to support industrial layout planning.
- X-RAPT: Enabled users to design XR-based training scenarios for robotics education.
- HEART: Combined VR and haptic gloves for training in precise remote manipulation tasks.
- SENSE-XR: Used XR and AI to improve safety in high-risk manufacturing, offering real-time alerts and evacuation support.

The key developments from these projects are integrated into the MASTER platform, creating a collection of validated XR assets for industrial and educational training. The winners of the 2nd Open Call will demonstrate how these XR-based modules can enhance learning experiences, providing evidence of their impact and scalability.

Stay Updated

Progress updates on the selected projects will be shared regularly via the [MASTER project's website](#) and its [LinkedIn channel](#).

About the MASTER Project

The MASTER project (“Manufacturing Education and Training through XR”) is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative dedicated to advancing robotics training in manufacturing through the use of Extended Reality technologies. By developing an open XR platform, MASTER aims to provide safe, adaptable robotic environments featuring advanced interaction mechanisms. Ultimately, the project seeks to empower non-expert programmers to create and manage XR educational content, contributing to a more skilled and technologically adept workforce.

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